

The production of a smartphone consumes around 920 liters of water [1].

The direct water consumption of a smartphone is around 20 liters per year, but indirect consumption through the use of data centers is many times higher [3,4].

2,5 years is the average lifespan of a smartphone in Germany [2].

There are around 200 million unused smartphones in German households [5].

References:

[1] Repedia. (2018, November 6). Wie viel virtuelles Wasser steckt in deinem Smartphone? Retrieved March 30, 2025, from https://repedia.de/en/blogs/blog/virtuelles-wasser-smartphone?srsltid=AfmBOorkHVISU4-XukVx6GENWUAfgoifi4S3DzB_dg-EVNGöwVfvtstl

[2] Wuppertal Institut für Klima, Umwelt, Energie gGmbH. (2024, June 13). Mehr Lebenszeit fürs Handy: Wie wir die Emissionen halbieren könnten. Idw - Informationsdienst Wissenschaft e.V. Nachrichten Aus Der Wissenschaft. <https://nachrichten.idw-online.de/2024/06/13/mehr-lebenszeit-fuers-handy-wie-wir-die-emissionen-halbieren-koennten>

[3] Sánchez, D., Baur, S.-J., & Eguren, L. (2020). Life cycle assessment of the Fairphone 5. Fraunhofer IZM. https://www.fairphone.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Fairphone5_LCA_Report_2024.pdf

[4] Derudder, K. (2023, November 10). What is the environmental footprint for social media applications? 2021 Edition. Greenspector. <https://greenspector.com/en/social-media-2021/>

[5] Meyer-Breitkreutz, N. (2020, April 16). Deutsche horten fast 200 Millionen Alt-Handys | Bitkom e. V. [Press release]. Bitkom. Retrieved March 30, 2025, from <https://www.bitkom.org/Presse/Presseinformation/Deutsche-horten-fast-200-Millionen-Alt-Handys>